

Career Management

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Abstract

The details fulfilled with about career management. The process involved in management and essentials of career planning bring out the skills and be adjust with others in the organization. A clear view of mapping, path interventions, and also situations in public organization well goes then career growth with career development.

Topics

- A. Career management
- B. Career management process
- C. Process
- D. Career management is essential to life
- E. Essentials for effective career planning
- F. Career skills
- G. Career adjustment
- H. Career mapping
- I. Career path interventions
- J. Challenges in public organizations
- K. 5 tips for career growth
- L. Career development

Career Management

- Career management is a combination of structured planning and the active management choice of one's professional career.
- A career includes any types of employment, ranging from semi-skilled through skilled, and semi-professional to professional.

Career Management Process

Career management is a life long process of investing resources to accomplish your future career goals. A career plan provides vision, structure & motivation of your career management process Focus on developing skills and knowledge for your current position also for future job opportunities.

Process

Self Assessment
Reality Check
Goal Setting
Action Planning

Self Assessment

Self-assessment motive will prompt people to query information to confirm their possible self-concept rather than their confident self-concept, and at the same time, people use self-assessment to enhance the certainty of their self-knowledge.

Reality Check

During this process, you will gather information on employment occupations, trends, companies, and the amount of education required.

The information will facilitate decision making & stimulate continued exploration allowing one to assess options and discover possible alternatives.

Goal Setting

Short term goals (one or two years) are regularly specific and limited in scope. Short term goals are more comfortable with formulating. Make sure there are achievable and relate to your longer-term career goals.

Long term goals (over 20 years) of course most fluid of all. Lack of life knowledge and experience about potential possibilities and pitfalls make the formulation of long term goals challenging. Long-range goals, however, may be easily modified as additional information is received without a significant loss of career efforts because of knowledge/experience transfer from one career to another.

Action Planning

A career improvement plan is a roadmap that will take you from point A (choosing an occupation) to point B (getting a job and advancing in your career).

An execution plan is a document that lists what steps must be taken to achieve a specific goal. An action plan determines to clarify what resources are needed to reach the goal. Formulate a timeline for when specific tasks need to be performed and learn what resources are required

Career Management is Important to Life

A high proportion of our life is spent in performing our career goals. Thus it is essential to make sure that the right steps were taken and correct planning was done in the early years of your life. There are extremely few lucky ones who are born with a sharp mind and who knows what they want to do and where they see themselves in life ahead. But the majority of us are not sure what we want from life, and so it is essential to plan out things. Thus career planning is what gibes your career and in some way, your life. True meaning and purpose.

Essentials for Effective Career Planning

- A personal vision for the future is key
- Self-awareness is essential
- Who you work with really matters
- Networking enhances growth
- Work the ethic counts
- Resume builder shape advantage
- Mentors and sponsors enhance the likelihood of success
- A board director serves well
- Risk-taking pays
- Continuous learning critical

Career Skills

Communication Skills

I am speaking, listening, and writing. Employers want people who can undoubtedly interpret what others are responding and organize and express their thoughts clearly.

Team Work

In today's work environment, various jobs involve working in one or more groups. Employers want someone who can take out the best in others

Career Adjustment

At times we may feel that the work which we are doing is not according to our choice. In that case, career adjustment becomes necessary.

Examples

After retirement, if a person is capable, he/she may take up some simple jobs. when work environmental becomes unsuitable. When there is no chance of advancement in the present career.

Career Mapping

A tool that managers and HR professionals can use during career planning disputes with employees.

It helps workers think strategically about their career paths and how to meet their career goals within the organization.

“Like a car GPS, career maps display alternative routes to build mastery in the care professions.”

Career Path Interventions

Career pathing often uses several development interventions as part of the process, these include;

Cross-training

Job rotation

Temporary assignments

Job enrichment or enlargement

Cross Training

Cross-trained workers have developed skills outside their current job assignment so they can be called upon to perform a kind of tasks as the need arises.

Job Rotation

A system movement of employees from job to job within an organization, where they are required to perform a variety of duties and have a range of skills and competencies

Job Enrichment

Involves increasing a worker's responsibility and control his or her work, and also called “vertical job loading.”

Job Enlargement

Involves increasing the number of tasks a worker performs, with all of the functions at the equal level of responsibility, and is also sometimes referred to as “horizontal job loading.”

Analytical Problem Solving Skills

Employers want people who can use reasoning, creativity, and past experiences to identify and solve problems effectively.

Interpersonal Effectiveness

Employers usually note whether an employee can describe to co-workers and build relationships with others in the organization.

Leadership Skills

The ability to take manage and charge your co-workers. If needed is a welcome trait. Most employers look for signs of leadership qualities.

Learning Skills

Jobs are continually growing and evolving. And employers want people who can learn and grow as changes come.

Academic Competence in Reading & Math

Although most jobs don't need calculus, almost all posts require the ability to read and comprehend instructions and perform basic math.

Strong Work Values

Self-Confidence, dependability, honesty, and a positive attitude are prized qualities in any profession. Employers look for personal integrity.

Challenges in Public Organization

- Slow advancement, where seniority has more value than merit
- There is a fixed order of development, independent of performance.
- There is a week of recognition of the individual merits of employees.
- Unclear career paths and insufficient career planning

5 TIPS for Career Growth

- think like a jobseeker
- learn to negotiate
- you can't grow alone
- I think beyond what you're paid to do
- book for a job with opportunities for growth
- Career Development
- Build your dreams
- Believe in yourself
- Never stop learning
- Sharpen your people skills
- Expand your network
- Find a mentor
- Build your reputation
- Stop telling & start selling